

EDUCATIONAL POTENTIAL OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN A HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION WITH A NON-LINGUISTIC PROFILE

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Digitalization has become an integral part of the modern existence of the world community. Today, digital technologies have become the most important component of our daily life and corresponding gadgets or electronic media in all spheres of life, including in the education system, are actively replacing paper media with digital equivalents.

At the present stage of development of society, innovations are actively being introduced into various areas of human activity, which requires from people, firstly, constant development and improvement of existing knowledge and skills, and secondly, creativity, creative thinking and willingness to cooperate. In this connection, digital learning technologies acquire particular significance. Thus, it is important to note that the New development strategy “Digital Uzbekistan-2030” has been approved for 2023 – 2030, aimed to informatization and digitalization of society [1]. This document also states that the country's population actively using digital resources should be at least 50% by 2025. This requirement clearly demands a significant restructuring in the education system associated with the use of digital technologies.

The use of digital technologies along with traditional ones will significantly increase the flexibility and technological effectiveness of education, as well as the motivational component of students for the educational process. The need to increase the motivational component is reflected in documents such as “Personnel and Education”, the “Digital Economy of Uzbekistan” program, which are aimed at increasing the motivation of employees temporary students to master digital competencies society [2].

One of the main elements of digitalization of education is digital literacy. Digital literacy is the main priority of education, this is the ability to design and use content using digital technologies, using computer programming, *graph visualization techniques*, computer graphics, multimedia development of online courses, etc., search and exchange of information, communication with other students. We define *digital literacy* as its various types: media literacy, attitude to innovation, communication, computer, information literacy. To solve the problems of digitalization, our education will have to go through digital transformation.

Today, all over the world, the ways of teaching foreign languages are changing daily due to technical and methodological changes in the learning process. The practical mastery of digital tools and materials by teachers and students represents both reality and prospect for their successful use in modern education [3].

A foreign language is an academic subject that involves the creation of an artificial language environment for students, which predetermines the variable inclusion of various digital learning tools in new prospects for teaching a foreign language. Digital learning tools are interactive systems that allow students to work simultaneously with animated computer graphics, sound, video frames, static texts and images. Student is influenced through various information channels, where user is assigned an active role [4].

In all the existing and constantly updated diversity, it is necessary to create and update in real time some typology of digital technologies in teaching a foreign language, determine the possibilities of their use and model methods of working

with them. Teachers see the prospect of successful implementation of digitalization of education in improving the material base, software and methodological support, and acquiring relevant experience.

The modern education system should be aimed at ensuring a confident transition to a digital society, which is characterized by economic growth and productive labor relations. As noted earlier, computers based on artificial intelligence are already actively used in the labor market, which successfully cope with routine work. The task of a modern person is to demonstrate creativity and creative thinking in order to create and introduce innovations [5].

Let us look at modern digital tools for teaching a foreign language and discuss some recommendations on methods of working with them in order to stimulate students' cognitive activity.

The first is a *multimedia lesson* – a training session using digital technologies, various programs and technical means for effectively influence on students. Tasks solved using multimedia in foreign language classes include:

- intensification of classroom work;
- stimulating real communication;
- providing information support;
- development of cognitive interest and motivation for learning a foreign language.

As practice shows, the introduction of such tools into the educational process, their use effectively affects the student, who develops the ability to understand the world around him, the skills of using knowledge and skills in a real life context; algorithmic thinking; creative thinking; making optimal decisions in a difficult situation; research skills; ability to process information. In addition, the teacher's adaptive abilities to the modern learning environment increase, non-stereotypical thinking and objective self-esteem are formed.

The second is an *electronic textbook* and various training programs that can be considered the most accessible multimedia tools for the student audience. Electronic software applications to the textbooks contain training programs for

memorizing words and grammar training, as well as additional practice in listening and writing. Curriculums have the ability significantly change the way learning activities are managed and carry out targeted individualization of learning, which helps improve the quality of learning. Working with programs helps students have better perceive new material thanks to graphic images.

The third digital tool is *multimedia presentations*, which are the next convenient technology to use in the educational process. For their usage, teachers need a computer and a projector. Presentations may be prepared in advance. The form of use of presentations during classes depends on the content of the lesson and its goals.

Let us consider the following effective goals for using presentations in the classroom:

- the process of illustrating and learning new material;
- consolidation of a new topic;
- checking the mastery of new material.

The next one is electronic testing – it is an automated tool for monitoring and assessing knowledge by a teacher or a self-control tool that provides visual control of the results.

Multimedia Internet resources – presents information interactively, visually, entertainingly, with instant feedback. Features of the functioning of Internet materials:

- 1) openness and accessibility for everyone, both for students and teachers;
- 2) free access of any educational materials;
- 3) the ability to quickly and easily create new digital objects: video and audio fragments, images and texts;
- 4) accessibility of any materials for people with different levels of knowledge and skills in the field of information technology.

All these materials exist, as a rule, in the original version in a foreign language and, therefore, can be used for foreign language classes to develop skills in working with a foreign language as a professional tool.

An educational video is a type of Internet resource that allows students to watch videos and complete assignments for them, which is used both online and offline. Tasks can be either included in a video recording or in special workbooks.

Digital classroom – among online resources, helps to create multimedia lesson plans and implement them into independent and classroom work of students, such as Google Docs or Google Docs. This is a free application that simulates MS Office online and includes a text editor, a spreadsheet editor, a service for creating presentations, and a cloud file storage service. Another advantage of the program is that it does not need to be downloaded and installed. Its use ensures communication between teacher and student in synchronous and asynchronous mode, allowing existing shortcomings to be instantly corrected; create individual and collective works; increase the volume of tasks solved *together with the teacher*.

Another online resource is Google Class, which offers free tools for working with email, electronic documents and cloud storage. Its advantages are:

- 1) convenient addition of students to the course system;
- 2) joining students to courses using code and working with several courses simultaneously;
- 3) creation of advertisements;
- 4) importing tasks;
- 5) joint teaching with a large number of colleagues;
- 6) creating templates and, therefore, reducing the time spent on creating tasks;
- 7) integration of additional materials with Google Drive.

The last one is *digital applications* are sites that allow teachers to create various types of graphic and text content for educational purposes.

The question of choosing methods for conducting training sessions is an everyday one, since specific training situations are very diverse. Cognitive technologies, including information, communication and digital technologies, are tools that help students develop memory and problem-solving skills. [6].

Digital technologies for teaching, monitoring, and demonstration purposes are being integrated into the teaching of various disciplines, including foreign languages. However, the characteristics of the course, the approaches used by the teacher, the level of requirements for the actual students' staff, and the form of training must be taken into account.

As a result of the study, we can conclude: the use of various services is effective means for creating presentations, video materials, and helps students learn new material with interest. The use of digital technologies opens up new opportunities for both teachers and students. Various information technologies make each lesson more vibrant, varied and memorable.

Digitalization of education leads to changes in the labor market, in educational standards, identification of needs for the formation of new competencies of the population and is aimed at reorganizing the educational process, The role of teachers creates the availability of information in its various forms, not only textual, but also audio and visual. Availability of information will require constant search and selection of relevant and interesting content, high speed of its processing. Consequently, the digitalization of education leads to its fundamental, qualitative restructuring. Teacher must learn to use new technological tools and practically unlimited information resources.

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